

State Versus Dynamic Variables, Special Relativity and Quantum Mechanics Part 2

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In this note we wish to focus on appropriate interaction based information in different states which are linked to each other and how this relates to free particle quantum mechanics. As in Part I, we considered the linking of states represented by different constantly moving frames (-v) and then generalized this to any constantly moving particle even with different rest masses. Here, we concentrate on the type of information one needs to track in terms of physical interactions and the possible independent features of variables. In other words, there may be different variables describing different kinds of interactions which are independent of each other. We suggest that this approach, the linking of states and retaining appropriate interaction information, leads to the notion of the quantum mechanical intervals $dt = \hbar/E$ and $dx = \hbar/p$.

We begin with the Lorentz invariant $-E^2 + p \cdot p = m^2 c^4$ and note that although this relates frames, it only contains a subset of interaction information because $p \cdot p$ holds for any rotated p , while a given set of p_x, p_y, p_z describes impulse hits against two dimensional targets in the $x-y$, $x-z$ and $y-z$ planes. As a result, one must retain p_x, p_y, p_z information, but must also relate it to E (energy information) because two particles with the same momentum might have different rest masses and hence different E values. This suggests a scalar equation which contains E, p_x, p_y and p_z . Such an equation already exists in special relativity, namely the Lorentz invariant $-E^2 + (p_x)x + (p_y)y + (p_z)z = \text{the same expression in another frame (different constant } -v)$.

Now x, y, z are trajectory points which transform under a Lorentz transformation, but we argue that the main issue with this equation is that it does show that p_x, p_y, p_z and E are independent from the point of view of their respective interactions. In other words, p magnitude already differs from E in terms of interactions in that it describes an impulse hit, whereas E is measured differently (distance traveled in a field). As noted, the same p (and hence same impulse) may be associated with different E values. Furthermore, given a p magnitude, different p_x, p_y, p_z values for the same p represent different impulse hits on the $y-z, x-z$ and $x-y$ planes. Thus, one must display the independence of these interactions from one another while still retaining their information. We suggest that this is done, not by using the 4-vector (x, ct) , but rather by the non-4 vector $(\hbar/(p_x), \hbar/(p_y), \hbar/(p_z), \hbar/E)$. This leads to independent units $(\pi) \hbar/\pi$ indicating interaction independence of p_x from p_y and p_z etc. There must, however, be an interpretation for the interval \hbar/π related to π . Given that π is interpreted as an impulse hit against a 2 dimensional plane, we suggest that \hbar/π represent an interval in which this impulse hit may occur.

This then leads to free particle quantum mechanics. In other words, we base this result on the notions of displaying the relevant information needed to describe interactions and their various independencies and the linking of states, in this case as in Part I, meaning any free particle states and not simply constant -v frames.

Interaction Information in Equations Relating Different States

Newtonian mechanics focuses on forces and their consequences. In particular, $dp/dt = \text{Force}$ shows how momentum changes when acted on by a force. Action-reaction deals with the consequences of force etc.

Special relativity, on the other hand, introduces the idea of an equivalence between different frames, in particular different constant $-v$ ones. In Newtonian mechanics, one would consider particles moving with different constant v values as consequences of different work applied to a particle m_0 at rest. Thus, there seems to be a different point of view used in special relativity which leads to results not seen in nonrelativistic Newtonian mechanics. (Galilean frames exist in Newtonian mechanics, but are not general enough.)

Here, we retain the notion of linking different states, but as in Part I, extend this to trying to link all free particle states. In order to link states, however, one must have variables describing the states. We suggest that one wishes to use variables which describe interactions and independent features in each state.

Appropriate Variables for Describing Free Particle States

If one considers the well-known Lorentz invariant:

$$-E^2 + c^2 \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{p} = -m_0^2 c^4 \quad ((1))$$

one sees that it contains E and $|\mathbf{p}|$ as information. We note that E^2 and $\mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{p}$ are separate terms. This is important because they describe different independent interaction information. $|\mathbf{p}|$ is proportional to the impulse hit against a two dimensional target perpendicular to the direction of the vector \mathbf{p} . E on the other hand, represents a combination of rest mass and work done on the particle and may describe how far it might move in a field before coming to rest etc. We note an independence between E and $|\mathbf{p}|$ because two different rest masses, m_{01} and m_{02} , may give rise to different E values, but the same $|\mathbf{p}|$. Thus, in one kind of experiment, target striking, one cannot distinguish between the particles, while in another (deceleration in a field), one can. Thus, one sees E^2 and $\mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{p}$ separated in ((1)) to show this independence, we argue.

The problem with ((1)), however, is that it does not contain all necessary interaction information. In particular, any (p_x, p_y, p_z) with the same $|\mathbf{p}|$ yields the same $\mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{p}$. Physically, however, p_x , p_y and p_z represent different independent impulses on an x - y , x - z and y - z plane. One should display this in an equation representing a state. In other words, E is a number, \mathbf{p} is a vector so one must use some kind of dot product with \mathbf{p} in order to include it in an equation containing E . This may be done using p_x, p_y, p_z , but at the same time one must demonstrate the independence of p_x , p_y and p_z among themselves and with E . As a result, we propose that one write an equation with p_x multiplied by $\text{constant}/p_x$ to represent an independent term. This describes the independence of the impulse hit of p_x from p_y and p_z . The same procedure is used for p_y and p_z and even E , leading to:

$$-E \text{ constant}/E + (p_x \text{ constant}/p_x + p_y \text{ constant}/p_y + p_z \text{ constant}/p_z) \quad ((2))$$

This, we suggest, describes a free particle state in terms of appropriate interaction variables and their independent features. The problem with ((2)) is that constant/E and constant/pi do not have explicit physical interpretations, they are simply math expressions.

Given that one takes a dot product with p (vector), constant/pi must be related to x,y,z axes. The question then becomes: What physical vector appears in the free particle scenario which may be used? The momentum vector has already been used. There only remains the r vector (x,y,z) which indeed appears in the Lorentz invariant:

$$-Et + \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{r} = -m_0 c^2 t \quad ((3))$$

This, however, does not demonstrate the independence of p_x , p_y and p_z values or of different E, m_0 values. We thus suggest that:

$$dx = \text{constant}/p_x, \quad dy = \text{constant}/p_y \quad \text{and} \quad dz = \text{constant}/p_z \quad ((4))$$

We note that ((4)) is not a 4-vector, but rather represents intervals in each frame which must have physical meaning. To be consistent, one should have:

$$dt = \text{constant}/E \quad ((5))$$

One generalizes the idea of constant -v frames to all free particles. In other words, in the rest frame, two different m_{01} and m_{02} values become related through:

$$-m_{01} c^2 / m_{01} c^2 = -m_{02} c^2 / m_{02} c^2 \quad ((6))$$

Thus, one relates different free particles in both different -v frames or with different m_0 values by equating ((2)) for these states.

Link to Quantum Mechanics

We still have not described the physical meaning of the intervals ((4)). It seems that a given p_x is linked with an interval dx etc. This interval was introduced in order to establish the physical independence of a p_x impulse hit on the z-y plane from a p_y one on the x-z plane and a p_z one on the x-y plane. We suggest that \hbar/p_x should be related to an interaction in the x direction just as p_x is. In the case of \hbar/p_x , this is an x interval, so we suggest that the interaction of p_x may act throughout this \hbar/p_x interval and not simply at the center-of-mass point, as is typically the case in both Newtonian mechanics and special relativity.

This then leads to the complex probability $\exp(-iEt + i \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{r})$ which we have discussed in previous notes.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we suggest that there are three key ideas to establishing quantum mechanics of a free particle. The first is the linking of different states, a concept which is introduced fully in

special relativity, although in this case the states represent E and p (as well as x, t and other 4-vector values) as seen from frames moving with different constant $-v$ values. (Galilean frames exist, but are not fully general.) The second notion is to describe the states by variables linked with interactions. This is also done in special relativity. $-E^2 + c^2 p \cdot p = -m_0^2 c^4$ links the variables E and $|p|$, both of which represent independent interaction information. $|p|$ is proportional impulse hit against a 2-dimensional plane perpendicular to the vector p , while E is linked to the distance a particle may travel in a field. It is possible to have E_1 and E_2 represent the same $|p|$ and vice versa, hence these are independent for different types of interactions.

The problem is $|p|$ represents many (p_x, p_y, p_z) vectors which represent different physical hits against x - y , y - z and x - z planes. One should explicitly display p_x, p_y, p_z . The Lorentz invariant $-Et + p \cdot r$ does so, but we suggest that a third idea is to demonstrate the independence of p_x, p_y, p_z in impulse interactions. As a result, we propose introducing the non-4 vector quantity: $\hbar/p_x, \hbar/p_y, \hbar/p_z$ (and \hbar/E). This shows that each $\pi(\hbar/p_i)$ unit is independent, but introduces a quantity \hbar/p_i which must have a physical interpretation. Given that p_i represent and impulse hit against a 2-dimensional plane perpendicular to p_i , and that there seems to be no other vector that (x, y, z) for a free particle (as the p vector has already been considered), one should consider \hbar/p_i to be an interaction interval in which p_x may act. This means that p_x no longer acts at a point (the center-of-mass of the particle), but rather over a region. This then explains the interaction with both slits of 2-slit apparatus if the slit widths/separations are of the order of \hbar/p_i .

Following this viewpoint, one develops free particle quantum mechanics.